

The Outdoor Learning Activities on EFL Vocabularies

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ABSTRACT: *This research was focus to find out the outdoor Learning activities on students' vocabulary of ninth grade students of SMAN 2 Sungguminasa. This research used pre-experimental method and the population of this research was the tenth grade students of SMAN 2 Sungguminasa Gowa South Sulawesi Indonesia in academic Year 2016- 2017. The Sample of this research used random sampling technique. In collecting the data, the research applied vocabulary test which consisted of two tests namely pre-test and post-test. The result of this research showed that the outdoor Learning activities can improve students' vocabulary mastery. It can be proven by the means score of pre-test and post – test where pre-test 50,63 and post-test 62,46 Post-test is higher than pre-test and t-test value is higher than t-table. The researchers concluded that outdoor Learning activities can improve students' vocabulary mastery of tenth grade students of SMAN 2 Sungguminasa Gowa South Sulawesi Indonesia.*

KEYWORDS-*Outdoor Learning Activities, EFL Vocabulary.*

I. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background

In order to be able to use the language productively, students must know certain amount of vocabularies, not only for communicating orally, but also in written. It is in line with the concept of communicative approach in which learners have a big chance to use the language directly in classroom activities.

How many words a student must know is varied. Kweldju (1997) found that the average vocabulary sizes of students from fifteen English Departments ranged from 2041 to 3352 words families. A study conducted to 1776 students in 21 state graduate schools in Indonesia showed that the graduate students' vocabulary size averaged 2861 words, while S2 students' vocabulary size 2671 words and S3 students' was 3211 words.

The complexity of vocabularies may cause the problem in the mastery. In English as a Foreign Language classroom, the most difficult aspects are the retention of vocabulary. Teachers work hard to improve the vocabulary of their students by using many methods and activities. Yet, this effort sometimes does not give good result because of the complexity of vocabulary learning in a foreign language. In increasing students' vocabulary there is a common problem faced by students namely they can't memorize the English word. Sometimes they memorize it easily and forget the words easily too. Besides, the learners study vocabulary just

focuses on their reference book. Consequently, they cannot practice their English because their vocabulary does not relate to their environment.

Based on the researcher surveys on SMAN 2 Sungguminasa the students found some difficulties in learning vocabulary in the class room. The teaching and learning activities make the student boring because the traditional way the teachers conduct in teaching such as get the students to translate the difficult words by looking on the dictionary, therefore the students creativity is shutting down. This problem also make the students are less attention on teaching learning activities. It also cuts their innovation to find more vocabulary.

To solve the problems, the researcher will try to use outdoor learning activities. It suggests letting the students to study on their environment in order to master on the related vocabulary. It is expected, the students are able to change their paradigm in learning vocabulary and the students will recognize that learning vocabulary should be based on their need in their real environment. At last they will practice it in their daily live.

Based on the clarification above the researcher writes this research with the title ‘The Outdoor Learning Activities on EFL Vocabularies.

1. 2 Research Question

From the explanation above, the researcher formulated the research question of this research:
Does the use of Outdoor Learning Activities improve the students’ vocabulary mastery at the ninth grade students of SMAN 2 Sungguminasa?

II. METHOD

2.1 Population and Sample

The population of this research was the ninth Grade students of SMAN 2 Sungguminasa in 2016/2017 academic year. It consisted of 6 classes and each class consisted of 30 students, so the total number of population was 180 students. The researcher used random sampling. The sample was taken fifteen students from IX A Grade and fifteen students from IX B grade. So, the total sample is 30 students.

2.2 The Instrument of the Research

The instrument of the research was vocabulary test. The test consisted of 15 items. It was divided into two parts, namely multiple choice and essay test. The tests were done twice. Both of them were pre-test and posttest. Pretest aimed to know the prior knowledge of students’ vocabulary mastery before treatment and the post test was done to know their vocabulary after doing treatment.

2.3 Procedure of Collecting Data

In collecting data, the researcher did the three steps. They are pretest, treatment, and posttest.

1. Pretest

Before giving treatment, the researcher gave pretest for students to find out the students’ vocabulary mastery before teaching by outdoor learning activities. It was done once.

2. Treatment

In giving the treatment, the research carried out the class in four times meeting. Each meeting, the researcher used outdoor learning activities in improving students’ vocabulary and each meeting run 90

minutes. The researcher explained about outdoor learning activities in simple sentence and then came to vocabulary test.

The Procedure of treatment was as follows:

The first meeting:

- a) The researcher divided them into six group discussions. Each group consists of five students.
- b) The researcher explained the outdoor learning activities in dealing with improving students' vocabulary mastery.
- c) Let the students got out from the class to discuss with their group and answer the questions that were given. Each group was given the table as follow:

Table 1
Work sheet paper

G	H	H	T	F
I	E	E	O	E
V	A	L	U	E
I	R	P	C	L
N	I	I	H	I
G	N	N	I	N
	G	G	N	G
			G	

The students were asked to fill the table with the words related to the environment around school area.

- d) The last, the researchers collected their worksheet and the researcher gave the correction of their exercises.

3. Post test

After giving treatment, the researcher gave post-test. The test was the same as pretest. It aimed at finding out the result of treatment. It was done once.

2.4 Technique of Data Analysis

The data were collected through the tests which were analyzed as the following procedure :

1. Scoring Test

To score the students' corrects answer of pre-test and post-test. The researcher used the following formula:

- a. Correct answer : 1
- b. Wrong answer : 0

2. Scoring the students correct answer of pretest and posttest by using the following formula :

- a. Correct answer : 1

b. Wrong answer : 0

3. Classifying the students' score as follows :

- a. Score 90-100 as very good
- b. Score 75- 89 as qualified as good
- c. Score 60-74 as qualified as fair
- d. Score 50-59 as qualified as poor
- e. Score 0- 49 as qualifies as very poor.

(Gay, 2004)

4. Calculating the mean score of students answer by using this formula

Where:

- M : Mean Score
- R : Total row students
- N : Total number of students

(Gay, 2006)

5. Finding the mean score of the different score by using formula :

Where:

- M : The mean score
- D : The sum of different score
- N : The total number of the sample

(Gay, 2006)

III. FINDINGS

3.1 Description of Pre-Test

Pre test was done once at April 29th 2017. It was done at tenth grade students of SMAN 2 Sungguminasa. The sample was taken randomly as been explained in the previous chapter.

In doing the pre-test, the researcher observed some students' bad habit in doing the test. They were:

- a) They were very noisy in doing the test.
- b) They did not understand well the question.
- c) The students cheated one to each other.
- d) They opened dictionary in doing the test.

These bad habits above shows their ability in English was very low. It also described, they had low motivation in learning English. In this situation, the researcher worked hard to keep the avoid students' bad habits by walking around the class and asked them to keep silent, no cheating and no opening dictionary. We also suggested them to do it based on their own mind.

Table 2
 Classification, frequency, score and percentage of the students pre-test result

No	Classification	Score	Member of students frequency	Percentage
1	very good	90-100	0	0 %
2	good	75- 89	3	10%
3	fair	60-74	8	26,6
4	poor	50-59	5	16,6
5	very poor.	0- 49	14	46,6
TOTAL	30	100%		

The data of table 2 above shows that, the rate percentage and frequency of students' pre-test in students' vocabulary mastery before using outdoor learning activities strategy that there were no students got "very good" score, 3 (10%) students got " good" score, 5 (16,67%) students got "good" score, 5 (16,67%) students got "poor" score and 14 (46,67%) students got very poor.

The conclusion of students' vocabulary mastery before having treatment by using outdoor learning activities was known from the average of students' score in pre-test ($x_{1=50,63}$) and from the data presented on the table 5 above. The value 50,63 ($x_{1=50,63}$) is classified as "poor". And then from the table five above, we see that 14 (46,67%) students got "very poor". It can be concluded that based on the average of students' score in pre-test ($(x_{1=50,63})$), the students' vocabulary mastery was categorized as "poor". But based on the classification on table 5 above, the students' vocabulary mastery before having treatment was "very poor". In the discussion, the important thing is the comparison of the average of students' score in pretest and post-test.

3.2 Description of treatment

After doing the pre-test, the researchers gave the students some treatments. Treatment was conducted for three meetings on may4th9th and 16th 2017.the treatment had been done as the planning in the proposal of the research.

On Thursday may 4th 2017 was the first meeting of treatment. The researcher explained about how important master the English in this globalization era. Then vocabulary is the main component of language.

Before going to the main activity, the researcher asked about the students' problem in learning vocabulary. From their answers, the researcher noted that the main problem in learning vocabulary was they could not memorize the word and sometimes they could memorize the words. It was caused by the vocabulary given had not practiced after they memorized. They could not practice it because the vocabulary given did not relate to their environment.

In the main activities, the researcher explained the outdoor learning activity strategy and provided the students' worksheet (treatment 1). Researchers remind them to respond the information from five human senses sensitively. We did not forget to ask them to bring the dictionary. Before

finishing the first meeting, we divided the students into 5 groups because the treatment was done in group.

On Thursday 9th 2017 was the second meeting of treatment. In this session, the students get out of class and found some unfamiliar words based on the five human sense responses. It was done with fun. Every student took a part actively in this session. The vocabularies found were classified into noun, adjective and adverb.

On Thursday 16th of May 2017 was the third meeting of treatment. In this session, the students were asked to exchanged their vocabulary list among groups, memorized the vocabulary based on the real object, corrected and commented their activities.

3.3 Description of Post-Test

Post test was conducted on Thursday 23th of May 2017. They were very surprised because the questions of pre-test and post-test was the same. In post-test, the situations were very different with the situations in pre-test. The students did not cheat, make noisy, open dictionary. They had changed their attitude after doing the treatment. The result of students' exercise in post-test is showed as follows:

Table 3

Classification, frequency, score and percentage of the students post-test result

No	Classification	Score	Member of students frequency	Percentage
1	very good	90-100	3	10 %
2	good	75- 89	4	13,3 %
3	fair	60-74	12	40 %
4	poor	50-59	3	10 %
5	very poor.	0- 49	8	26,7%
TOTAL	30	100%		

The data of table 3 above shows the rate percentage and frequency of students' post-test in students' vocabulary mastery after using outdoor learning activities strategy that there were 3 (10%) students got "very good" score, 4 (13,3%) students got "good" score, 12 (40) students got "fair" score, 3 (10%) students got "poor" score and 8 (26,7%) students got very poor.

The conclusion of students' vocabulary mastery after having treatment by using outdoor learning activities was known from the average of students' score in pre-test ($\sum X_{2=62,46}$) and from the data presented on the table 9 above. The value 62,46 ($\sum X_{2=62,46}$) is classified as "fair". And then from the table three above, we see that 12 (40%) students got "fair". It can be concluded that the students' vocabulary mastery after having treatment was "fair".

3.4 simulation score

The researcher presents the simulation score of students' pre-test and post-test as the table 4 below.

Table 4
The simulation score of students' pre-test and post-test

Situation of Score	Number of students	Percentage
Develop	26	86,67%
Unchanged	4	13,33%
Decrease	-	0%
Total	30	100%

The table 4 above describes that, there are 24 (86,67) students develop their score after having the treatment and there are 4 (13,3) students unchanged their score and no students decreases their score.

IV. CONCLUSION

Vocabulary is the key component of languages. Before the learners learn more about a language, they have to master vocabulary, especially the vocabulary that they need in their daily conversation. To answer the problem statement of this research, the researcher has collected some data. After collecting data, it can be seen that there is significance different of students' vocabulary skill in pre-test and post-test. It is shown by the mean score of pre-test and post-test. The conclusions of the data collection are as follow

1. The comparison of the average of students' score between pre-test and the average of student' score in post-test. It has been calculated before that the average students score in pre-test is 50,63 ($x_1=50,63$). This value is classified as "poor". Then, the average students score in post-test is 62,46 ($x_2=62,46$). It is classified ad "poor". We can see that the average of students' score in pre-test and post-test are classified as "poor", it does not mean that outdoor learning activities can not improve students' vocabulary because the average of students' score in post-test is higher than the average of students' score in pre-test ($x_2 > x_1$ or $50,63 > 62,46$).
2. The comparison of the students' score classification between pre-test and post-test. From the table 4 above, we see that, there are 24 (86,67) students develop their score after having the treatment and there are 4 (13,3) students unchanged their score and no students decreases their score. Considering two points have been mentioned above, the researcher concluded that Outdoor learning strategy can increase students' vocabulary mastery.

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